

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Antibacterial spectrum of medicinal plants: A review

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Abstract

Medicinal plants exerted their antibacterial effects through many mechanisms included inhibition of cell wall synthesis, inhibition of cell membrane synthesis, disruption of cytoplasmic membrane, inhibition of bacterial proteins synthesis, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, inhibition of energy metabolism, as well as inhibition of bacterial virulence factors. The current review highlighted the medicinal plants with antibacterial activity with their spectrum of action.

Keywords: Medicinal plant; Herbs; Natural, Pharmacology; Antibacterial

1. Introduction

The antibiotic- resistant bacteria in different communities was increased as a result of excessive use of antibiotics [1-11]. Using of medicinal plants represented an alternative choice for natural and synthetic antibacterial drugs in medical practice to avoid the development of multi-drug resistant bacteria[12-15]. Medicinal plants exerted their antibacterial effects through many mechanisms included inhibition of cell wall synthesis, inhibition of cell membrane synthesis, disruption of cytoplasmic membrane, inhibition of bacterial proteins synthesis, inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, inhibition of energy metabolism, as well as inhibition of bacterial virulence factors [16-20]. The current review highlighted the medicinal plants with antibacterial activity with their spectrum of action.

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Table 1 Antibacterial spectrum of medicinal plants

Plants	Bacterial Spp	Gram-negative	Gram-positive	Antibacterial Spp	References
<i>Achillea santolina</i>				✓	21-22
<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i>	✓			✓	23-25
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	✓	✓		✓	26-29
<i>Agropyron repens</i>				✓	30-31
<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	✓		✓		34-36
<i>Aihagi graciorum</i>	✓			✓	37-41
<i>Allium cepa</i>			✓	✓	42-47
<i>Allium porrum</i>			✓		48-49
<i>Allium sativum</i>	✓		✓	✓	50-62
<i>Alpinia galangal</i>			✓		63-68
<i>Aithaea officinalis</i>	✓		✓	✓	69-71
<i>Aithaea rosea</i>	✓		✓		72
<i>Annonavia baccifera</i>	✓		✓	✓	73-75
<i>Anoni visnaga</i>	✓		✓	✓	76-78
<i>Anagyris foetida</i>			✓		79-80
<i>Anchusa strigosa</i>	✓		✓	✓	81-82
<i>Anethum graveolens</i>			✓	✓	83-85
<i>Anthemis nobilis</i>	✓		✓		86-89
<i>Anatyrhinum majus</i>	✓		✓	✓	90-91
<i>Apium graveolens</i>	✓		✓	✓	92-95
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	✓		✓	✓	96-97
<i>Arctium Lappa</i>	✓		✓	✓	98-100
<i>Artemisia campestris</i>	✓		✓	✓	101-102
<i>Arundo donax</i>	✓		✓	✓	103-104
<i>Asclepias curassavica</i>	✓		✓	✓	105
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	✓		✓	✓	106-107
<i>Avena sativa</i>			✓	✓	108-109
<i>Bacopa monniera</i>			✓		110-112
<i>Ballota nigra</i>			✓	✓	113-115
<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	✓		✓	✓	116-117
<i>Bellis perennis</i>			✓	✓	118-121
<i>Benincasa hispida</i>	✓		✓	✓	122-124
<i>Betula alba</i>	✓		✓		125-126
<i>Bidens tripartita</i>	✓		✓		127
<i>Brassica rapa</i>	✓		✓	✓	128-129

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References	Bordetella Spp	H. pylori	Corynebact. Spp	Listeria monocitogenes	Mycobacterium	Peptostreptococcus	Clostridium spp.	Prevotella spp.	Bacteroides spp.	Streptothomonas	P. aeruginosa	Vibrio Spp	Enterobacter Spp	Acinetobacter spp.	Proteus spp.	Serratia spp.	Citrobacter spp.	Enterobacter spp.	Klebsiella spp.	Shigella Spp	Salmonella Sp.	E. coli	H. influenza	E. faecalis	Micrococci Spp	Staph. epidermis	Staph. aureus	Staph. aureus (MRSA)	Strept. faecalis	Strept. pyogenes	Strept. pneumoniae	Viridans group strept.	B-hemolytic strept.	a-hemolytic strept.	Bacillus Spp	Plants			
130-133																																						<i>Bryophyllum calycinum</i>	✓
134																																						<i>Caesalpinia crista</i>	✓
135-139																																						<i>Calendula officinalis</i>	✓
140-143																																						<i>Calotropis procera</i>	✓
144-145																																						<i>Canna indica</i>	✓
146-149																																						<i>Capparis spinosa</i>	✓
150-154																																						<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	✓
155-158																																						<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	✓
159																																						<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	✓
160-161																																						<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>	✓
162-167																																						<i>Carum Carvi</i>	✓
168-170																																						<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	✓
171-174																																						<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	✓
175-176																																						<i>Celosia cristata</i>	✓
177-179																																						<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	✓
180-185																																						<i>Chenopodium album</i>	✓
186-188																																						<i>Chrozophora tinctoria</i>	✓
189																																						<i>Chrys. cinerariaefolium</i>	✓
190-193																																						<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	✓
194-201																																						<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	✓
202																																						<i>Cistanche tubulosa</i>	✓
203-208																																						<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	✓
209-241																																						<i>Citrus Species</i>	✓
242-246																																						<i>Clerodendrom inerme</i>	✓
247-251																																						<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	✓
252-253																																						<i>Colchicum balansa</i>	✓
254-255																																						<i>Convolvulus arvens</i>	✓
256-259																																						<i>Corchorus aestuans</i>	✓
260-261																																						<i>Corchorus capsularis</i>	✓
262-263																																						<i>Cordia myxa</i>	✓
264-278																																						<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	✓
279-263																																						<i>Coronilla varia</i>	✓
283-284																																						<i>Cotoneaster racimiflora</i>	✓
285-286																																						<i>Cressa cretica</i>	✓
287-288																																						<i>Crocus sativus</i>	✓
289-292																																						<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	✓
293-313																																						<i>Cuminum cuminum</i>	✓
314-322																																						<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	✓

2. Conclusion

The development of resistant bacterial strains is one of the major public health problem. Plant extracts have shown inhibitory effect on the growth of wide range of bacteria by many mechanisms. They are represented a good alternative for prevention and treatment of bacterial diseases.

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